

Synthesis, structural characterization and luminescence behavior of a mononuclear zinc(II) iodide complex containing a tetradentate Schiff base

Bhola Nath Sarkar, Subhasis Roy, Smita Satapathi, Rajarshi Ghosh, Kishalay Bhar and Barindra Kumar Ghosh*

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

E-mail : barin_1@yahoo.co.uk Fax : 91-342-2530452

Manuscript received online 01 August 2012, accepted 21 August 2012

Abstract : A pentacoordinated mononuclear compound of the type $[Zn(L)(I)]PF_6$ (**1**) [$L = N,N'$ -(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,4-butanediamine] has been isolated using one-pot reaction of the building components. The complex is characterized using microanalytical, spectroscopic and other physicochemical results. Structure of **1** is solved by single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. Structural analysis reveals that the metal center in **1** adopts a distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry with ZnN_4I chromophore. Intermolecular C-H...F hydrogen bonding interactions lead to a 2D sheet structure. **1** shows thermal stability up to 280 °C and displays intraligand $^1(\pi-\pi^*)$ fluorescence in solid state at room temperature.

Keywords : Mononuclear zinc(II), iodide, Schiff base, X-ray structure, luminescence.

Introduction

Construction of self-assembled coordination molecules and supramolecular entities¹ of varied nuclearities formed through control and manipulation of strong metal-ligand covalent bonds² and multiple weak non-covalent forces^{1,3-5} is the center of attraction to the coordination chemists for preparation of different varieties of functional materials⁶⁻⁸. One-pot synthesis⁹ using metal ions, organic spacers and suitable terminal/bridging units in pre-assigned ratios is an efficient approach to isolate such target molecules. Schiff bases^{10,11} are important organic ligands because of their ease of preparation, structural varieties and varied denticities. Halides^{12,13} are suitable terminal and/or bridging units which in combination with organic blockers may control nuclearities and structural diversities resulting in different coordination molecules and supramolecular entities. Zinc(II)¹⁴⁻¹⁶ with its d^{10} configuration permits a wide range of symmetries and coordination numbers and it has significant use in bioinorganic chemistry¹⁷. Earlier, we reported the synthesis, structural characterization and property of a zinc(II) thiocyanate complex¹⁸ in combination with the Schiff base, N,N' -(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,4-butanediamine (**L**, Scheme 1), which prompt us to investigate the chemistry

of zinc(II) halides with this Schiff base. Successfully, we have isolated a mononuclear compound, $[Zn(L)(I)]PF_6$ (**1**) and X-ray crystallographically characterized. The details of synthesis, the crystal structure and thermal and luminescence behaviours of these compound are described below.

Scheme 1. (N^P, N^i, N^i, N^P) set in **L**.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The pentacoordinated mononuclear compound $[Zn(L)(I)]PF_6$ (**1**) was isolated as colorless crystals through one-pot synthesis of 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of the respective ZnI_2 , **L** and NH_4PF_6 from methanol-acetonitrile (1 : 1) solution mixture at room temperature. The reaction is summarized in eq. (1) :

1 was characterized by microanalytical (C, H and N), spectroscopic, thermal and other physicochemical results. The microanalytical results are in good conformity with the formulations of **1**. The moisture-insensitive complex is stable over long periods of time in powdery and crystalline states and is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide. In MeCN solution, **1** behaves as 1 : 1 electrolyte¹⁹ (vide Experimental).

Spectroscopic studies :

In IR spectrum, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ plus $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching vibrations of the metal-bound Schiff base are observed within 1630–1590 cm^{-1} range²⁰. Additionally, presence of hexafluorophosphate stretches at ~ 840 and 555 cm^{-1} (vide Experimental) is indicative of non-coordination²⁰ to the metal center. X-Ray study corroborates this hypothesis. Colorless DMF solution of compound **1** shows ligand-based transition at 298 nm presumably due to $n-\pi^*/\pi-\pi^*$ transitions²¹.

Luminescence property :

The photoluminescence behaviours of the free Schiff base ligand (L) and its corresponding zinc(II) halide compound (**1**) were studied in solid state at room temperature (298 K). The spectral patterns are shown in Fig. 1. Upon photoexcitation at the corresponding absorption band (280 nm), free ligand exhibits a fluorescent emission centered

Fig. 1. Solid state fluorescence behaviours of L and compound **1**.

at 423 nm. On the other hand, the compound **1** shows a more intense photoluminescence characteristics with main emission centered at 424 nm upon excitation at the corresponding absorption band (350 nm) of the compound. The greater intensity of luminescence behavior in **1** may be attributed^{22,23} to the metal-perturbed intraligand $^1(\pi \rightarrow \pi^*)$ transition becoming more permissible upon coordination of the Schiff base.

Thermal property :

TG-DTA curve shows that pyrolysis of **1** starts around 280 °C (Fig. 2). The weight loss (obs. 69.1%; calcd. 72.2%) within the temperature range 280–650 °C is associated with the simultaneous decomposition of the Schiff base and one terminal halide in a continuous fashion with an endothermic effect at 314 °C. The thermal study reveals that compound **1** has reasonable thermal stability. The final residue of the pyrolysis process of **1** corresponds to a zinc nitride (obs. 25.32%; calcd. 32.30%).

Crystal structure :

In order to define the coordination sphere conclusively, single-crystal X-ray diffraction measurement of **1** was made. ORTEP diagram with atom numbering scheme and perspective view of the crystalline architecture in **1** are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. Selected bond distances and bond angles relevant to the metal coordination sphere and the non-covalent bonding parameters are set in Tables 1 and 2.

The structure of **1** (Fig. 3) consists of $[\text{Zn(L)(I)}]^+$ cation and PF_6^- as counter anion. The zinc(II) center in **1** has a distorted trigonal bipyramidal (tbp)²⁴ [$\tau = 0.54$] geometry with ZnN_4I chromophore ligated by four N atoms (N1, N2, N3 and N4 of L) and one terminal halide. One N^{p} (N1) and one N^{i} (N3) atom [$\text{N}^{\text{p}} = \text{N}(\text{pyridine})$ and $\text{N}^{\text{i}} = \text{N}(\text{imine})$] of the Schiff base along with the terminal halide define the equatorial plane and the remaining N^{p} (N2) and N^{i} (N4) atoms of the Schiff base occupy the axial sites. The larger ionic radius of iodide results in longer Zn-I distance [2.6125(5) Å] over Zn-N bond lengths (Table 2). L forms two five-membered and one seven-membered chelate loop around zinc(II) center. The butylenic arm (N4-C18-C19-C20-C21-N3) of the Schiff base in **1** is to some extent puckered. The zinc(II) center departs 0.043 Å from the mean plane (N1, N3, I1) towards the axial N4 atom.

Fig. 2. Thermal behaviour of 1.

Fig. 3. The asymmetric units for the complexes 1. Displacement ellipsoids are drawn at 30% probability for all non-hydrogen atoms.

Fig. 4. A view of 2D sheet structure in 1 formed through C-H...F hydrogen bondings in *bc*-plane.

Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for 1

Bond distances for 1		Bond angles for 1	
I1-Zn1	2.6125(5)	N1-Zn1-N3	118.27(11)
Zn1-N3	2.088(3)	N3-Zn1-N2	76.99(11)
Zn1-N4	2.157(3)	N3-Zn1-N4	89.52(11)
Zn1-N1	2.078(3)	N1-Zn1-I1	110.82(8)
Zn1-N2	2.154(3)	N2-Zn1-I1	98.92(8)
		N1-Zn1-N2	99.31(11)
		N1-Zn1-N4	78.06(11)
		N2-Zn1-N4	163.16(11)
		N3-Zn1-I1	130.80(8)
		N4-Zn1-I1	97.53(8)

Table 2. Hydrogen bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for 1

Compd.	D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
1	C6-H6...F4 ^a	0.93	2.53	3.254(4)	136
	C7-H7...F3 ^a	0.93	2.49	3.316(4)	149
	C13-H13...F2 ^b	0.93	2.54	3.434(4)	162
	C14-H14...F4 ^c	0.93	2.51	3.385(5)	158
	C24-H24...F1 ^d	0.93	2.53	3.337(4)	146

Symmetry codes : a = 1+x, y, z; b = 3/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z; c = 1/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z; d = 1/2+x, 1/2-y, 1/2+z.

The mononuclear units of 1 are self-assembled through weak C-H...F hydrogen bonds in *bc*-plane forming a 2D sheet structure (Fig. 4). The shortest intermolecular Zn...Zn separation is 8.243 Å.

Conclusion :

A luminous zinc(II) iodide compound in combination with a tetradentate N-donor Schiff base has been isolated

and X-ray crystallographically characterized. The structure of **1** represents reliability of the combination of strong covalent bonds and weak non-covalent interactions in crystal engineering for the rational design of functional materials at molecular level.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 1,4-butanediamine (Lancaster, UK), 2-benzoylpyridine (Lancaster, UK), zinc(II) iodide (SRL, India) and ammonium hexafluorophosphate (Fluka, Germany) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. The Schiff base, *N,N'*-(bis(pyridine-2-yl)benzylidene)-1,4-butanediamine (**L**) was prepared by condensation of a 1 : 2 molar ratio of 1,4-butanediamine and 2-benzoylpyridine following the reported procedure²⁵. All other chemicals and solvents used were AR grade. The synthetic reactions and work-up were done in open air.

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectrum (KBr discs, 4000–400 cm^{-1}) was recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FTIR model RX1 spectrometer. Molar conductance was measured using a Systronics conductivity meter where the cell constant was calibrated with 0.01 M KCl solution and MeCN was used as solvent. Thermal study was made with a Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DT analyzer heated from 30–700 °C under nitrogen. Ground state absorptions were measured with a Jasco model V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Solid state fluorescence measurement was done using a Hitachi Fluorescence Spectrofluorimeter F-4500.

Preparation of the complex :

$[\text{Zn}(\text{L})(\text{I})]\text{PF}_6$ (**1**) : **L** (0.418 g, 1 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 ml) was added dropwise to a solution containing ZnI_2 (0.319 g, 1 mmol) followed by NH_4PF_6 (0.163 g, 1 mmol) in methanol (20 ml). The final light yellow solution was filtered and left for slow evaporation in air. After a few days colorless crystals of **1** that separated, were washed with hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. The yield was 0.529 g (70%) for **1** (Found : C, 44.3; H, 3.5; N, 7.6. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{F}_6\text{PIZn}$ (**1**) : C, 44.5; H, 3.5; N, 7.4%); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ 1627, 1595; $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ 843, 557; UV-Vis (DMF, $\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$) : 298; Λ_{M} (MeCN, $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) : 125.

X-Ray crystallographic analysis :

Diffraction data of the single crystals of **1** were collected at 150(2) K on a Bruker AXS SMART APEX-II CCD area-detector diffractometer using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation. The unit cell parameters were obtained from SAINT²⁶ and absorption corrections were performed with SADABS²⁷. The structure was solved by direct methods and refined by full-matrix least-squares method based on $|F|^2$ using SHELXL-97²⁸. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters. The H atoms were placed in calculated positions ($d_{\text{CH}} = 0.97 \text{ \AA}$ for methylene and 0.93 \AA for phenyl) after checking their positions in the difference map. The U_{iso} values were constrained to be $1.2U_{\text{eq}}$ of the carrier atoms for all H atoms. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-97, SHELXTL²⁸, Mercury 2.3²⁹ and ORTEP-3³⁰ programs. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure determination parameters is given in Table 3.

Table 3. Crystallographic data and structure refinement parameters for **1**

Complex	1
Formula	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{F}_6\text{PIZn}$
Formula weight	755.77
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P21/n$
a (Å)	8.6557(8)
b (Å)	19.2896(18)
c (Å)	17.5816(16)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	102.3130(10)
γ (°)	90.00
V (Å ³)	2868.0(5)
λ (Å)	0.71073
$\rho_{\text{calcd.}}$ (g cm^{-3})	1.750
Z	4
T (K)	150(2)
μ (mm^{-1})	2.054
$F(000)$	1496
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.28 \times 0.19 \times 0.06$
θ ranges (°)	1.59–26.31
$h/k/l$	–10, 10/–24, 24/–21, 21
Reflections collected	22614
Independent reflections (R_{int})	5821
T_{max} and T_{min}	0.88 and 0.63

Table-3 (contd.)

Data/restraints/parameters	5821/0/370
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.210
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R = 0.0368$ and $wR = 0.0603$
R indices (all data)	$R = 0.0561$ and $wR = 0.0647$
Largest peak and hole ($e\text{\AA}^{-3}$)	-0.635 and 0.751
Weighting scheme : $R = \sum F_o - F_c / \sum F_o $, $wR = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum w(F_o^2)^2]^{1/2}$, calcd. $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F_o^2) + (xP)^2 + yP]$; $x = 0.0000$ (for 1) and $y = 0.0000$ (for 1), where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.	

Supplementary materials :

Crystallographic data for the structural analyses have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center No. 826783 (**1**). Copies of this information can be obtained, free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

Acknowledgement

Financial support from the CSIR, New Delhi, India is gratefully acknowledged. SS and KB are grateful to the CSIR, and SR to UGC, New Delhi, India for fellowships. The authors also acknowledge the use of DST-funded National Single Crystal X-ray Diffraction Facility at the Department of Inorganic Chemistry, IACS, Kolkata, India for crystallographic study.

References

- J. W. Steed and J. L. Atwood, "Supramolecular Chemistry", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 2009.
- H. A. Habib, B. Gil-Hernández, K. Abu-Shandi, J. Sanchiz and C. Janiak, *Polyhedron*, 2010, **29**, 2537.
- G. A. Jeffrey, "An Introduction to Hydrogen Bonding", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1997.
- F. Awwadi, R. D. Willett and B. Twamley, *Cryst. Growth Des.*, 2011, **11**, 5316.
- M. Nishio, M. Hirota and Y. Umezawa, "The CH/ π Interaction", Wiley-VCH, New York, 1998.
- X.-L. Yang, M.-H. Xie, C. Zou, Y. He, B. Chen, M. O'Keefe and C.-D. Wu, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 10638.
- S. Horike, K. Kishida, Y. Watanabe, Y. Inubushi, D. Umeyama, M. Sugimoto, T. Fukushima, M. Inukai and S. Kitagawa, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 9852.
- M. Petty, "Molecular Electronics : from Principles to Practice", Wiley, Chichester, 2008.
- H.-B. Yang, K. Ghosh, Y. Zhao, B. H. Northrop, M. M. Lyndon, D. C. Muddiman, H. S. White and P. J. Stang, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 839.
- P. A. Vigato, S. Tamburini and L. Bertolo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **251**, 1311.
- K. Bhar, S. Khan, J. S. Costa, J. Ribas, O. Roubeau, P. Mitra and B. K. Ghosh, *Angew. Chem.*, 2012, **124**, 2184.
- U. Englert, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **254**, 537.
- Z. M. Lighvan, A. Abedi and M. Bordar, *Polyhedron*, 2012, **42**, 153.
- P. Jiang and Z. Guo, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**, 205.
- W. Huang, H.-B. Zhu and S.-H. Gou, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 414.
- C. Nazikkol, R. Wegner, J. Bremer and B. Krebs, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1996, **622**, 329.
- A. S. Prasad, "Biochemistry of Zinc", Plenum, New York, 1993.
- S. Das, K. Bhar, S. Chattopadhyay, P. Mitra, V. J. Smith, L. J. Barbour and B. K. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 2012, **38**, 26.
- W. J. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
- K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds, Part B", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, 2009.
- A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York, 1984.
- J. R. Lakowicz, "Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy", 3rd ed., Springer, USA, 2006.
- X.-J. Yang, X. Liu, Y. Liu, Y. Hao and B. Wu, *Polyhedron*, 2010, **29**, 934.
- A. W. Addison, T. N. Rao, J. Reedijk, J. V. Rijn and G. C. Verschoor, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1984, 1349.
- S. H. Rahaman, R. Ghosh, D. Bose, H.-K. Fun and B. K. Ghosh, *Struct. Chem.*, 2006, **17**, 460.
- G. M. Sheldrick, SAINT, V4 : Software Reference Manual Siemens Analytical X-ray Systems, Madison, WI, USA, 1996.
- G. M. Sheldrick, SADABS : Program for Empirical Absorption Correction of Area Detector Data, University of Göttingen, Germany, 1996.
- G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 2008, **A64**, 112.
- C. F. Macrae, P. R. Edgington, P. McCabe, E. Pidcock, G. P. Shields, R. Taylor, M. Towler and J. van de Streek, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 2006, **39**, 453.
- L. J. Farrugia, ORTEP-3, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1997, **30**, 565.

